

Concept of Blue Economy - a Qualitative Review for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

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Abstract:

Ever since the Blue economy concept emerged, there were speculations on its potentials to diversify Nigeria's economy and be used as alternative source of revenue. This paper qualitatively and descriptively examined the prospect and challenges of the concept through reviews and practices by nations that have ventured into it. It identified the areas of opportunities and strength by interviewing selected community members across selected coaster states in Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted to select Apapa in Lagos, Okerenkoko in Delta, Oron in Akwa Ibom, Agge in Bayelsa and Bonny in Rivers State. Secondary data was also used to

determine the correlation between revenue from the maritime industry and Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria. It can be observed that, Nigeria stands to benefit a lot from Blue economy concept from hydro-electricity, pharmaceutical, exportation, tourism, e.t.c. However, it may be a dead end investment if care is not taken to properly weigh it opportunities, cost and financial requirements. Arrays of factors must be put into consideration before embarking on it like security, fund, bunkering, smuggling and Foreign Direct Investment. Ocean and maritime resources should be explored without degradation to marine ecosystem.

Keywords: *Blue Economy, potentials, GDP, marine, development, Nigeria.*

Introduction

The two major provisions for existence of man and other living things revolve around heat and water. Heat is necessary for cooking, powering engines, drying and other activities either generated from the sun, electricity or hydrogen cell. Water is used for digestion, as coolant, in planting and without which survival may be

difficult. Water resources are so numerous and beneficial to mankind. The motivation for this research emanated from the realization of Nigeria's potential as a coaster state that fail to utilize and maximize the ocean or water resources to its economic advantage.

According to Commonwealth (2023) Blue economy is referred to as an emerging concept

which is focused on the sustainable exploration or exploitation of ocean resources. The worldwide ocean economy is said to be \$1.5 trillion per annum as the 7th in the order of economic ranking in the world. Since 80% of goods by volume is through the sea, water resources have potential to generate economic growth through employment, food security and social well-being without degradation to the marine ecosystem (Commonwealth, 2023). Crude oil, fishes, water and some products are derivatives of the marine system. World Bank (2017) reiterated that, blue economy is capable of influencing exchange rate, enhance economic development, and reduce poverty, increase equality, marine energy, fisheries and marine technology.

Nigeria is one of the world's oil producing countries in the world. In Africa, Nigeria is first in petroleum production with 77.9 metric tonnes followed by Libya (59.6 metric tonnes), Algeria (58.2 metric tonnes), Angola (56.6 metric tonnes), Egypt (29.6 metric tonnes), Congo 14 metric tonnes, Gabon metric tonnes, South Sudan 7.5 metric tonnes, Equatorial Guinea 6.4, metric tonnes Chad 6.1 metric tonnes, others 14 metric tonnes (Statista, 2021). This oil is gotten through exploration of marine resources at different oil fields in Nigeria. Before the discovery of oil, Nigeria is known for exportation of agricultural products like cocoa, cashew nut, coal, bauxite, timber, leather, sesame seed, seafood and others (Adeloye, 2012; NCEMA, 2008).

Nigeria's economy's boom witnessed in the 1970s because of oil discovery has nose-dived to recession and at the moment in comatose state. The problem as expressly explained by Katsouris and Sayne (2013) presented to the Royal Institute of International Affairs emanated from the various dimensions of oil theft in industrial scale in Nigeria. The authors noted that organized crime in oil theft from Nigeria to other countries can be traced to the military officers, oil industry personnel, politicians, militants, communities through taping to oil pipes, organized boats and exportation through terminals. While some refine locally, government inept ability to manage, be proactive and enforce

policies that stimulate transparency and accountability worsen the Nigerian economy. The money transactions in Nigeria's oil market make use of foreign banks which reduces the value of Naira daily. Bribery of bank officials, smuggling, bunkering and piracy, militancy, terrorism and drug trafficking are all connected with oil theft especially in the coaster areas in Nigeria. Hitherto, the country's refineries are not working while Dangote multi-purpose refinery is set to commence operations.

Bassey (2023) reported that, export trade will boost the economy and intra-African trade. The challenge with export trade in Nigeria centers on expiration of goods before they get to their final destination. According to Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) (2023) there is increase in export promotion by 31% ranging from fertilizer, agricultural goods and precious stone. Other products exported from Nigeria are beans, prawn, cocoa butter, ginger, palm kernel, African textile, rubber, and garlic, yam tubers to countries like Brazil, China, Turkey, UAE, France, Estonia, India, USA, Vietnam, Belgium, Netherlands, Indonesia and Spain. Nigerian government in the past had tried various management strategies to boost her economy through Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), Nigerian Export-Import Bank, e-Naira, establishment of Nigerian Export Promotion Council and recently joined African Free Trade Economic (Babawole, 2020).

Examining the trend of pre-oil discovery and oil discovery in Nigeria suggested a critical question of whether the resources for economic development is or are not adequate or there was and has been the mismanagement of the resources. In the case of the former, the concept of blue economy can be explored to further strengthen the Nigerian economy and in the latter case, the management, enforcement and leadership strategies should be investigated. While the latter may be challenging, the aim of this research is to identify the potential areas of blue economy and correlate the marine revenue with the GDP to determine the direction of maritime industry's impact on national development.

Advantages, Potential and Challenges of Blue Economy

Blue economy is related with the use of ocean and water resources for the benefit of mankind. Apart from the use of water for drinking; cleansing and for irrigation. It is essential to explore the use of water resources for aquaculture in terms of fishery, regulation of current or climate, and make use of its in-depth resources for other use in biotechnology, pharmacy, and medicine and hydroelectricity generation. The extent to which blue economy can be useful has not been revealed (Adepoju et al, 2023). Blue economy according to Manso et al (2023) has the potential to provide electricity if well utilized. Hamisu (2019) reiterated the number of employment that can be generated with the use and implementation of blue economy in Nigeria. It is not gainsaying fact that, Nigeria can diversify its economy through blue economy especially starting with littoral states without much dependence on crude oil.

Literature Review

The concept of Blue economy is derived from the realization that oceans have valuable assets. However, exploiting the ocean and other water resources has significant effect on environment, marine ecosystem and climate change (UN, 2012). The meaning and perspectives given to blue economy can be succinctly summarized into having a sustainable ocean resources exploited without degrading the marine ecosystem, capable of providing equity, nutrition, environmental friendliness, jobs and social welfare to mankind (Juneja et al, 2021, World Bank, 2017). While attempting to explore the concept of blue economy- it is imperative to distinguish between live able economy and unlivable planet. Activities of man surrounding burning, waste disposal on water, pollution, production and noise are inimical to marine environment and ecosystem. According to Juneja et al, 2021) it is interesting to note the wide interest in ocean and water resources for exploration for sustainable economic development but the term “blue economy” in

use has become problematic. The reason is because there seems not to be boundary and possibility of measuring level of success and how to evaluate contributions on the concept on the economy. In the brief report of World Bank for Blue economy resilient for Africa, it was reported that Blue economy generated over \$300billion for African continent in the year 2018. It generated about 49million jobs with other benefits like food security, livelihoods and tourism (World Bank, 2019).

UNESCO (2021) presented a technical report on blue economy opportunities in Gulf of Guayaquil in line with the realization of sustainable development goals’ agenda of the United Nations. Peru and Ecuador signed agreement to combat hunger, malnourishment and to promote aquaculture with coaster and marine ecosystem sustainable management. The method used for identification of opportunities was through spatial planning to strategically denote fisheries, tourism, aquaculture, oil and gas, renewable energy, deep sea exploration and maritime transport. Appiah et al (2023) applied Structural Equation Modeling to determine the investment opportunities in Ghana’s Blue economy concept with results indicating that: organizational factors, technology, risk in terms of green environmental control and policy as instrument of regulation have influence on investment on Blue economy and preservation of marine ecosystem. European Commission (2023) provided analysis of contributions of Blue economy to four major countries like Spain, Italy, France and Germany in direct and indirect employment opportunities and how it has helped in spite of recession caused by COVID 19 to the European economy.

Examining publications in Web of Science, Manso et al (2023) assessed the trend of future researches in Blue economy and found out that, for economic progress attention has been focused on climate change; blue growth, marine spatial planning and private administrative concerns. Fudge et al (2023) assessed the blue economy in coaster areas with three criteria based on their well-being of (1) relational (2) subjective and (3) material aspect. It was observed that, people in marine communities

value their relational and subjective well-beings compare with material aspect.

Fudge et al (2023) examined the community's interest in blue economy agenda. It was found out that people's interest and relational experience with marine environment is more important than material aspect. Again, the research confirmed that, developing marine industries may negatively affect relational experiences of marine community and therefore consequences of adverse effects on their connection without reasonable care.

Using the sea or ocean to foster economic development in Nigeria should not be a difficult thing to do so if all challenges to achieving this have been removed. It is important to understand the benefits that can be derived from this blue economy. According to World Bank (2016) illustrating the various segments of benefits in the blue economy can be succinctly described as follows:

Blue Economy can be Used to Generate Hydro-Electricity

Blue economy can be developed to generate electricity throughout all the littoral states. Today, the country is experiencing challenges in the area of power generation, transmission and chiefly in distribution (Manohar and Adeyanju, 2009). Sharma and Sharma (2003) decried how potential hydro-power sites are underdeveloped in Nigeria. Kainji, Jebba and Shiroro are the hydro-generating electricity stations whereas other power plants like Sapele, Egbin, Afam and Ughelli are gas generating stations under their respective generating companies (Gencos). Nigeria is blessed with dams, lakes and rivers that can be used for power generation more than as it is currently. Energy Studies Institute published an article in May, 2021 of how Singapore was set to explore blue economy by generating solar power through the use of ocean around the country. Of a reference was the positioning of Tidal Energy Site at Sentosa Boardwalk in September 2019 which is converting kinetic energy in flowing water into electricity for the purpose of charging batteries and other local use. This is a concept from Ocean Renewable Energy (ORE). In other

words, it harnessed power from waves, tidal current, temperature and ocean salinity gradients. The dimension that deep blue project will take if fully explored in Nigeria is yet to unfold. In 2018, Singapore was able to generate solar power through solar photovoltaic (PV) and offshore wind.

"In March 2021, Sunseap Group installed a 5MWp offshore floating solar farms in Singapore. As one of the largest floating PV projects in the world, it is expected to produce around 6 million kWh of energy per year and offset an estimated 4,258 tonnes of carbon dioxide- Quirapas-Franco et al (2021)".

Sea Foods

There are sea foods that are useful for mankind usually gotten from the oceans and rivers around us in Nigeria. In the United States, seafood supported 1.2 million jobs. There are best seafood species in Nigeria. They are rich in calcium and other organic minerals. Fishes, Cray fish, crabs, prawn, periwinkles and other kinds of seafood are not only nutritious, they are recommended for healthy living (Adepoju, 2023). Blue economy can project seafood to the local areas and beyond the shore lines at affordable rate for social and economic development of Nigeria. Looking at the local consumption of seafood in Nigeria against the population of the country, it is obvious there is need for us to put more effort in this direction. The seafood should be raised not to the detriment of its ecosystem sustainability but in a way that, outside the seabed, local fish farm and other allied seafood can be developed. This will not only provide affordable protein for healthy living but also and jobs for economic development. Seafood is one of the income generating sources for the Gross Domestic Product of Portugal. All restaurants dealing with tourists in the land must make use of seafood to welcome their customers. It has been confirmed that, more than half of the fish trade emanated from the waters of developing countries (World Bank, 2016).

Industrialization through Cluster

This suggests that, wherever there is oceanic exploration activity, there must be attraction of industries. This is because of the accessibility to raw materials and clusters it formed closing to other allied industries. The emergence of blue economy can allow many other smaller and bigger industries to come up. By so doing, there will always be economic expansion. (Hamisu, 2019)

Tourism and Recreation

Tourism is an area that has not been fully explored in Nigeria. Tourism rejuvenates soul and enhances natural well-being of man. The blue economy may look at tourist sites and during certain festive or holiday period it can be subsidized. Recreation centres are sources of income for individual and can be enhanced through blue economy for the purpose of commercialization by the government too. Transport acts in two different forms when it comes to tourism: There is Transport for tourism and also transport as tourism (Camileri, 2018). Transport for tourism connotes the use of transport for the purpose of tourism. i.e it is a means to an end and the satisfaction derived is related to cost and speed of travel, so the mode of travel has no direct intrinsic value in itself (Page, 2009). However, transport can serve as the basis for tourism when for instance cruising is used as a mode of transport for tourist experience. Either way, the experience of tourists when transport serves as tourism or for tourism will have influence on whether to continue in tourism or not.

Areas that can be developed in blue economy for tourism include Cinemas, sport and ferry services which are built around serene water environment. Today, Singapore uses Deep Tunnel Sewage System to produce very clean sustainable water. This is a process whereby there is collection of disposed used water from industries, homes and businesses which is treated to meet the clean water needs of the island (Yin, 2018). Tourism can be categorized into natural, cultural, indigenous, rural, business, medical, sport and coaster tourism. There is no one among the mentioned types of tourism that

is not tangentially related to blue economy. However, there is hardly anyone fully exploited as a result of weakness in operational procedures to fully understand the necessity and impact of tourism on revenue generation and natural renaissance in Nigeria.

Import-Export

This is an area where Nigeria needs to package, rebrand and preserve her products for exportation in global value supply chain. The DG World Trade Organization, Mrs Ngozi Okonjo Nweala reiterated what Nigeria needs to do in this direction. There are products that are should be expunged rotten away annually in Nigeria which we need to find means to preserve and for us to reduce the influx of imported items' consumption with possibility of substituting them with locally produced ones wherever possible. According to World Integrated Trade Solutions (WITS), there are many products that Nigeria imports from different countries of the world ranging from categorization as follows: Animal, Vegetable, Food products, Minerals, Fuels, Chemicals, Plastics or Rubber, Hides and Skin, Wood, Textile and Clothing, Foot wear, Stone and Glass, Metals, Machinery and Electricals, Transportation and equipment, Agricultural raw materials, Iron and ores etc. Somuyiwa et al, 2021)

However, the Nigerian Export Promotion Council (2019) highlighted the following commodities that Nigeria exports are: Cashew nut, Ginger, Crude oil, dry bean, cocoa, leather and sesame. Though Nigeria's crude oil reserves are expected to last another 40 years, all indications are that oil prices will continue to crash and with the emergence of alternative energy sources and increased focus on electric cars, oil will cease to play a prominent role in the international market which has implication on maritime logistics trade (Awolowo, 2019).

Recently, the former Vice President of Nigeria (Prof. Yemi Osinbajo) inaugurated expanded committee on sustainable blue economy in Nigeria. This was to give weight to the laudable project of the Blue economy with backing from African Development Bank, governors of

Lagos, Ogun, Rivers, Bayelsa, Delta, Edo, Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Ondo and Borno States. Apart from this, private sectors and government agencies like Nigerian Port Authority, Nigerian Inland Water ways Authority and Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agencies (NIMASA) are all part of the project. He noted the areas of benefits and to be further explored as fishing, tourism, renewable energy, marine biotechnology, training, ports, and Oil and gas sectors. According to The Guardian (2021), Blue economy is capable of generating revenue, providing jobs for unemployed youths and foster Foreign Direct Investments. The Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria can actually be enhanced by the formidable force of Blue economy. The benefits of blue economy are still evolving. This is because, when sea and water resources are being utilized for the economic progress of Nigeria, other innovations and allied industries development will definitely emerge. According to the statement of David Hume (2020) which can be paraphrased thus:

“A nation that trades with large export and import must generate abundant number of industries and enjoy luxuries and delicacies than a nation or kingdom that rest and contented with its native commodities without exploration and exportation. Such a nation will grow powerful, richer and happier”

In other to maximize the potentials of blue economy, Nigeria needs to be positive to see the future of all commodities needed to be projected for the rest of the world to demand. It is regrettable that, a country among the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries like Nigeria will still be refining her petroleum products in abroad to import refined product back to the county. Nigerian oil rigs are not controlled by our people rather some are owned and controlled by foreigners. Ethanol, according to EIA is a renewable bio-fuel as it is made from biomass. In the United States, ethanol fuel is made from biomass materials referred to as feed stocks (Babatunde, 2022). Similarly, starch and sugar content feed stocks such as corn, sorghum, barley, sugarcane or sugar beets of which Nigeria is richly blessed are sources of bio-fuel in developed world. Bio-fuel can also be made

from agricultural residues like sawdust, rice straw, grasses and wood chips. Corn has been the major feedstock for ethanol production in U.S because it is relatively cheap and abundant (Babatunde, 2022). Most other countries in the world make use of sugar cane and fermentation process in production of ethanol. Brazil is the second largest producer of ethanol after United States and, she produces mostly through sugarcane (Lorrenz and Morris, 1995).

Pharmaceutical

The benefit of blue economy in the production of pharmaceuticals and ancillary services through biotechnology cannot be over emphasized. The production of chemicals and health care products with the development of bio-medical services is the advantage of blue economy. This may further enhance research and development in herbal and natural medicine (Adepoju, 2023).

Oil and Gas

The Oil and Gas sector has been the major source of income for Nigeria since the discovery of crude oil in the '70s (AfDB, 2009). There is possibility of change in narrative with the blue project through economic recovery plan which will showcase unfathomable segments in off-shore and on-shore activities. The economic boom expected of the blue project will pave way for private partnership and private investors for the purpose of economic recovery and employment generation (DESA, 2017). The control of oil rigs and its management must be properly guided with polices that can enhance economic development (Elisha, 2019). It is very unfortunate that, Nigeria in this modern age refines her petroleum product abroad and incurring cost on refinement in foreign exchange value and shipment. If conglomerate can build refinery and hopefully maintain and manage it, then probably the government should lease out the refineries with good polices to back it up against exploitation. Today, issue of subsidy removal has been the strategy to be adopted by successive government for economic liberalization. This ideology is predicated on forces of demand and supply. That is, fuel price or petroleum products prices will be regulated

when free forces of demand and supply set in. The question that keeps coming to mind is in the area of economic inflation (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2015). Secondly, does it mean Nigeria's refineries cannot function again? For how long are we going to be exporting to be importing our refined products? Transportation cost is one of the factors influencing socio-economic cost. This cost is indirectly influenced by cost of energy required to propel transport vehicles (oil and gas). Therefore all other costs relating to distribution, exploration, consumption and even disposition will go up once the price of fuel is increased. While believing in blue economy to stem the tide of dependence on crude oil, it must be used along with blue economy till will get to full realization of mass production in blue governance.

Marine Ecology Theory

Ocean and marine system can be said to be responsible for climate change, most energy generation, food, natural resources and transportation by water (Visbeck, 2018a). Human activities like fishing and extraction of resources from the ocean resulted in over fishing and pollution with negative effects on economy and environment (McIntyre, 1995).

Fashchuk (2011) pointed out that United Nation has recognized the need for transition from random exploitation of natural resources to sustainable development of mankind. It suggests a systematic approach for future generations on contemporary economic management to satisfy human needs. The concept of sustainable development in this regard as noted by World Commission of Environment and Development (1987) suggested that:

- a) The rate at which the renewable resources consumption should not be more than the rate at which the natural renewable resources are depleted.
- b) Technology and other method of developments in the production of non-renewable resources artificially should be higher than the rate at which they are depleted.

- c) The rate and quantities of waste deposits and industrial waste should not be more than what the environment can accommodate.

Measuring these items across the space of marine ecosystem especially in Nigeria is a very serious task. Theorizing this concept has been found to be easier than its practicality with the Summit by Heads of States in Johannesburg, 2002 where it was observed that, its implementation faced some challenges. According to Fashchuk (2011), there is a wide gap in level of knowledge and ignorance about ocean resources and ecology from various practitioners and supposedly experts in the industry. In furtherance to his inquisitiveness, marine ecosystem is being seen from the surface and people living in the area without proper understanding why the marine ecosystem is made of what and reasons for change occurrence by external force so far we can blindly kill nature for the purpose of future prosperity without learning. It is very difficult to predict and understand the marine ecosystem dynamics without understudying it by analyst and expert. The postulations on blue economy and marine ecosystem for diversifications of economy failed to provide how the resources are to be tapped or what resources are present with accurate quantities, time and seasonal changes occurrence but surface value promises that may not be realistic in implementation. Fashchuk (2005) reiterated that, computer and mathematical modeling concepts are now used to estimate and understand the functioning of marine ecosystem.

Marine ecology presents itself with shelf at different zones within time and space. Obtaining information can be accessed with spatial planning with observations of variability in structure, basin, and topography, abiotic and biotic components of the marine ecosystem.

Sustainable Development of Blue Economy in Line with UN Development Goals

Sustainable Development Goals as stated by the United Nations are seventeen in number. The

goal ranges from ensuring that there is no poverty, zero hunger to good health, education, gender equality, water cleanliness, affordable energy, a work environment that is decent, sustainable cities (11), responsible consumption (12), climate change or action (13), life below water (14) and life on land (15) which are just essentials for this study. In general, a balanced life will guarantee all these sustainable development goals. Blue economy in this case is to maximize the utilization of water resources in our environment to achieving the stated sustainable development goals.

Countries that Have Practiced and Still Exploring Blue Economy

Indonesia focused her blue economy on the developing marine and fishing industries. Japan focused on reducing plastic waste on its blue economy, Cambodia capitalized on developing marine resource, food security and pollution control. Australia managed its blue economy to

foster marine assets and technology for safeguarding on a long term health. China created 13 year plan for employment growth in blue economy (Juneja, etal, 2021). Bangladesh held Blue economy ministerial conference in 2019 to growth employment opportunities along Indian oceans. India's blue economy was developed through inter-ministerial economic advisory council with the aim to develop a blue economy working report for accounting, tourism, shipping, fishery, spatial mapping and other shipping strategy on Indian Ocean. Sri Lanka initiated its Blue economy concept in 2016 but yet to fully develop it till date. Malaysia has explored blue economy concept in energy production through refineries and petroleum product from offshore and tourism (Cheryl, 2015). Globally, shipping production by Asian countries like Japan, Korea and China represent about 90% (Juneja,2021). Mayhew et al (2014) explained that, Australia developed 40% of its Exclusive Economic Zone for conservation of marine resources in Blue economy, Canada 7.7%, Chile 43% among other nations.

Figure 1. Coaster States in Nigeria
 Source: Adapted from Katsouris & Sayne (2013)

Methodology

Survey conducted across the communities in littoral states in Nigeria. Figure 1 below shows the geographical map of the coaster areas in Nigeria along which the sampled communities were selected. Using multi-stage sampling techniques; nine States were identified in Nigeria for economic water resources beneficial to Blue Economy by this research. The states are Lagos, Bayelsa, Delta, Rivers, Akwa Ibom, Cross River Ondo States, Kogi and Benue States. Five of the States were randomly selected to meet with the communities at the coaster areas. The selected five are Lagos, Bayelsa, Delta, Rivers and Akwa Ibom. Major communities nearest to the riverine areas or marine environments were selected across the states. The communities are Apapa in Lagos, Yenegoa in Balyesa, Okerenkoko/Warri in Delta, Bonny in River State and Oron in Akwa Ibom State. The last stage was to identify at least five most educated persons across communities for interrogations and triangulations.

Interview questions were structured for all the selected communities to provide relevant information on the concept of Blue economy in Nigeria. Responses were recorded for easy translation and data analysis. Generally, the questions ranges from *awareness of Blue economy, potentials of Blue Economy, Effect of Blue economy, challenges of Blue economy, how to diversify Nigeria's economy and marine resources they feel present in their waters*. Secondly, descriptive statistics was used to present secondary data generated from Statista(2022) website and Nigerian Ports Authority on Gross Domestic Product and revenue from Maritime activities in Nigeria.

Results and Discussions

Responses generated across the selected communities were generally analyzed for better results and findings. Specifically each of the 5 persons across the selected communities responded to questions as follows:

Okerenkoko (Delta States)

General responses from respondents: Three out five respondents (60%) are not aware of any concept called blue economy.

“Generally, everywhere you see water has potentials for example fishing, crude oil, e.t.c as we have here. Naturally if blue economy is about marine resources exploration, we have been doing that, but it has effect on our water because of oil pollution, no much fishes in the water. The challenge is that people will over do things and see how it is difficult for us to get things cheaply here unlike in Warri. Nigeria can diversify her economy by insisting foreign countries pay us in Naira equivalent of what they buy from us. Let them be looking for Naira too! Let Nigeria reduce her spending and prioritize on major demanding ones. We should focus on exportation and consume what we produce locally. We have crude oil, fishes, shipping business and may be many people will get job through shipbuilding if Blue economy can be implemented”.

Bonny (Rivers State)

General Responses from respondents: Still following the order of the questions. 4 persons among the selected five have fore knowledge of Blue economy concept (80%). Blue economy has been heard of but it is just a concept to deceive people and embezzle funds. What should be explored from oceans and rivers have been identified long ago and they seem not to think that any difference can be made. Effect of blue economy has been observed also just that, this time it will increase the attention of government to protect marine environment and also over explore the resources in sea bed. If other areas in marine operations like we constructing ships can be developed the better. The challenges are the same just that, corruption will increase, pollution will increase and bunkering may increase too. Nigeria can diversify by not focusing on crude oil but on other resources and agriculture through technology. Of course Rivers State is known for crude oil and among oil producing states in

Nigeria. There is opportunity of direct shipment from abroad, fishes and other petro-chemical resources.

Lagos (State)

General Response from respondents: All the persons selected surprisingly attested to the concept of Blue economy (100%) in Apapa area of Lagos State. Blue economy is popular here with the advocacy by Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA). Well, its potentials have been severally enumerated on media regarding job opportunities and diversification of revenue from oil to other areas in maritime sector. But it is easier said than done! They believe maritime sector can actually generate revenue to finance budget if properly harnessed. There seems not to be any negative effect when the government can put in place policy to control how water and ocean resources can be accessed and explore. It can foster development of tourism, international trade, specializations and ocean resource management. The challenges are in the implementation, security and corrupt practices. It can also be seen in form of pollution and take a look at sewage disposal on waterways in the country, it is a bane to the development of better ocean economy and concept of blue economy. Nigeria can only diversify truly by foreign direct investment, export promotion, consumption of local products and earnings in Naira equivalent of dollar currency like some countries in developing nations.

Akwa Ibom

Three out of four respondents claimed that they are aware of the concept of Blue economy (80%). Those who are conversant with the concept opined that, Blue economy is a welcome development. It is a long overdue strategy to diversify the Nigerian economy. According to them, it can foster the development of hydro-electricity projects which is one of the major problems in Nigeria, export promotion of best crayfish and sea foods across the world, employment of seafarers, boat repairers and allied opportunities. They suggested opportunities embedded in tourism and recreation with maritime blue economy concept

development. The challenges remain the same as in the maritime environment in terms of security, bunkering, pollution and smuggling.

Agge (Bayelsa)

Three persons out of five sampled attested to the knowledge of Blue Economy concept in the region making about (60%). All the five persons however believed that Agge and its environs have potentials for Blue economy in the areas of hydro-power generation, employment opportunities, deep seaports establishment, marine business and international trade. Challenges noted here cut across political will, finance, community rivalries, and transportation by rail and getting investors. Nigeria can diversify her economy through foreign direct investment, export management and payments in Naira equivalents of Dollar transactions. Most persons suggested the exploration of ocean resources, fishing, oil and gas exploration, export and petro-chemical industries for the development of the area and the state at large.

Arising from the above findings, it can be succinctly concluded that; blue economy concept is perceived to be beneficial to the host communities in littoral states across Nigeria. However, the challenges involved must be studied and ways of overcoming them must be of priorities to the government, people and maritime stakeholders.

Table 1. Maritime Revenue and GDP in N Billion Converted to Have \$ and \$Billion Respectively

Year	GDP US Billion S	
2010	0.168417	369.06
2011	0.1917	414.10
2012	0.226683	460.95
2013	0.262183	514.97
2014	0.288	568.5
2015	0.295333	492.44
2016	0.304033	404.65
2017	0.442667	375.74
2018	0.450933	421.74
2019	0.4628	448.12
2020	0.528333	429.42
2021	0.548333	441.42
2022	0.601667	477.38

Source: Statista (2022); NPA (2022); NBS (2021)

The secondary data generated for the Gross Domestic Product of Nigeria and the revenue in maritime sector was presented in the Table 1.

Table 1 above presented the revenue in the maritime sector in comparison with the GDP of Nigeria. While it can be observed that there is sharp rise in the GDP of the country between

2012 and 2016 observable years, the GDP declined possibly because of economic recession and COVID 19 witnessed between 2016 and 2019 and started picking u in 2020 to maintain a slowly steady growth till 2022. The Maritime industry has over the years under review witnessed progressive but slow rate of increase in revenue (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. GDP and Revenue from Maritime industry description

This study has shown that, there areas that can be exploited to the advantage of Nigeria’s economy with Blue economy concept. Conversely, it can be fathomed out that; there is no significant correlation between the GDP of Nigeria and the revenue from maritime industry. Though, there is progressive slow progress steadily made cross the years under review but economic development is beyond certain prediction of a singular concept. All the communities could not be covered by this research but the sampled served as representative can be extended to other coaster areas to mirror realities of economic development.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Blue economy is a good concept and has been practiced in other nations of the world. Its potentials across the coaster and maritime domains in Nigeria should be realized and the peculiarities of interest of various selected communities should be observed. However, it may be a dead end investment if care is not taken to properly weigh it opportunities, cost and financial requirements. Arrays of factors must be put into consideration before embarking on it like security, fund, bunkering, smuggling and Foreign Direct Investment. There were instances of suggestions by the communities for export promotion, use of locally made products, exchange rate and others. Blue economy alone cannot sustain the economy but working around it with other sectors can immensely improve the

standard of living of not only the coaster areas communities but by extension the nation at large. This paper recommends that, blue economy should be strategically tried at specific communities before extending to general interest areas. More importantly, the exploration for Nigeria's economic development should include:

- a) Fishery and fish farming
- b) Energy and dam for power generation
- c) Pharmaceutical technology and renewable energy
- d) Tourism and recreation
- e) Irrigation and agriculture

Future research can examine the areas of weaknesses and what could hinder the possibilities of blue economy to come to realities so as to prepare against it in case of its implementation.

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